

Material Name	Material Type (Format)	Description	URL/Persistent Identifier
Schedule	Information (PDF)	Schedule for the workshop providing a breakdown of topics and timings	Included in this Zenodo record
Working with DNA sequences and features in R with Bioconductor - version 2	Online tutorial (webpage)	Online tutorial on which this workshop is based. Tutorial includes slides, exercises and example code.	Available via Monash Data Fluency https://monashdatafluency.github.io/r-bioc-2/